

Alkaloids of *Argemone mexicana*

Sarita Singh, Tryambak Deo Singh, Virendra P. Singh and Vidya B. Pandey*

Department of Medicinal Chemistry, Institute of Medical Sciences, Banaras Hindu University,
Varanasi-221 005, Uttar Pradesh, India

E-mail : pandeyvb@gmail.com Fax : 91-542-2367568

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Abstract : Four isoquinoline alkaloids *dl*-tetrahydrocoptisine, dihydrocoptisine, 8-methoxydihydrosanguinarine and 13-oxoprotopine have been isolated from the whole plant of *Argemone mexicana* and their structures have been established by spectral evidences. This is the first report of these alkaloids from *Argemone mexicana*.

Keywords : *Argemone mexicana*, isoquinoline alkaloids, *dl*-tetrahydrocoptisine, dihydrocoptisine, 8-methoxydihydrosanguinarine, 13-oxoprotopine.

Introduction

The plant *Argemone mexicana* Linn. (Papaveraceae) is an annual herb naturalized throughout India. It is an erect, approximately 1.2 m in height with prickly leaves, bright yellow flowers and seeds resemble black mustard seeds. It is used in the treatment of fever, pain, diarrhoea and cancer in Indian system of medicine^{1,2}. A number of alkaloids³⁻⁶, flavonoids^{7,8} and other constituents^{9,10} have been reported earlier.

Here, we report the isolation and characterization of *dl*-tetrahydrocoptisine, dihydrocoptisine, 8-methoxydihydrosanguinarine and 13-oxoprotopine from the whole plant of *A. mexicana*. The identities of these compounds were confirmed by IR, UV, ¹H NMR, Mass spectroscopy and direct comparison (m.p., m.m.p., co-TLC and superimposable IR) with authentic samples. This is the first report of the occurrence of these alkaloids in *A. mexicana*.

Experimental

The whole plant of *Argemone mexicana* was collected from Varanasi district, Uttar Pradesh, India and identified by Prof. N. K. Dubey, Department of Botany, Banaras Hindu University, Varanasi. The whole plant (2.5 kg)

dried and powdered was extracted with MeOH in a Soxhlet extractor. The MeOH extract was evaporated to dryness, which furnished brown gummy mass (270 g). The MeOH extract was then extracted with 7% aqueous citric acid repeatedly. The combined acidic solution was basified with ammonia and extracted thoroughly with CHCl₃. The CHCl₃ fraction was evaporated to dryness, which furnished a brown semi-solid crude base fraction (12.6 g).

The crude base fraction was chromatographed over SiO₂ gel column eluting with solvents of increasing polarity. The eluants were collected and monitored by thin layer chromatography at every stage for their homogeneity. The eluants from C₆H₆-CHCl₃ (1 : 1), (1 : 2), (1 : 99) and CHCl₃-MeOH (95 : 5) on evaporation and crystallization of the residues from MeOH, furnished respectively the alkaloids, *dl*-tetrahydrocoptisine¹¹ (25 mg) (1) as colorless shining needles, m.p. 220–222 °C; dihydrocoptisine¹² (18 mg) (2) as light brown granules, m.p. 235–237 °C; 8-methoxydihydrosanguinarine¹³ (21 mg) (3) as pinkish yellow granules, m.p. 195–197 °C and 13-oxoprotopine¹⁴ (19 mg) (4) as colorless granules, m.p. 225–227 °C. These were identified by the physical properties, spectroscopical characteristics (UV, IR, ¹H NMR, MS) and by direct comparison (m.m.p., co-TLC and superimposable IR).

(1)

(2)

(3)

(4)

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